

**PULMONARY EMPHYSEMA. ETIOLOGY, PATHOGENESIS,
CLASSIFICATION AND CLINIC. DIAGNOSIS AND COMPLICATIONS,
PRINCIPLES OF TREATMENT**

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Abstract. This article describes in detail about pulmonary emphysema, its etymology, pathogenesis, classification and clinic, as well as diagnosis and complications, principles of treatment.

Key words: pulmonary emphysema, etymology, pathogenesis, clinical diagnosis, diagnostic analysis, principles of treatment, etc.

Pulmonary emphysema and pneumosclerosis can be divided into acute and chronic depending on how it progresses, and depending on how widespread it is, it can be divided into focal or diffuse types. Emphysema and pneumosclerosis often appear in places affected by toxic substances in patients with chronic bronchitis, bronchial asthma, acute and chronic pneumonia, pulmonary tuberculosis. In the development of the disease, the violation of bronchial permeability and a decrease in lung elasticity are considered important. An emphysematous lung expands in size: if such a lung is removed from the chest, it will not collapse even if it loses its elasticity. The lungs become anemic because the capillaries are atrophied. Along with the expansion of the lungs, the chest also expands, the diaphragm descends, and the rib cages ossify (turn into bone) early. Secondary hypertension occurs within the small blood circulation, gas exchange in the lungs is severely derailed. Deformation of the chest and spine is of some importance. The narrowing of the small bronchi leads to the first swelling of the lungs, and then to the appearance of organic changes.

Patients with emphysema complain of worsening shortness of breath. Most of them have a cough (dry cough or cough with sputum). The appearance of the patient is characteristic: the face is bruised and puffy, the neck is shortened, and the neck veins are bulging. The chest expands significantly in the forward-back direction, and often becomes barrel-shaped. Breathing is superficial, inhalation is short and slow exhalation is prolonged and can occupy three quarters of the entire breathing. The lungs produce a box-like sound when percussed. Lung excursion is reduced. During auscultation, it is known that the breath has slowed down.

Sometimes dry wheezes are heard. The heart sounds are muffled, the II tone accent that appears in the pulmonary artery as a result of pressure increase in a small circle is felt. Lung capacity decreases. Cardiovascular system examination reveals muffled heart sounds, tachycardia, heart borders may be enlarged to the right. As pulmonary emphysema worsens, the pressure in the microcirculation increases, which puts extra pressure on the right ventricle and causes it to hypertrophy. Later, failure of this ventricle of the heart occurs, which continues along with the enlargement of the liver and swelling of the body. X-ray examination. It can be seen that the clarity of the lung tissue has increased and the pulmonary artery is clearly visible. Treatment. Treatment of pulmonary emphysema and pneumosclerosis depends on the cause of the disease. Treatment measures should be aimed at restoring the permeability of bronchial passages. Oxygen therapy is beneficial in complex treatment. Breathing exercises help improve lung ventilation. Therapeutic gymnastics is aimed at improving the movement of chest muscles, diaphragm and ribs. Consequence: depends on the development of the main disease. Prevention. Prevention of the disease depends on its timely detection and treatment. If the disease is related to harmful occupational factors, it is necessary to improve working conditions and transfer the patient to lighter work. Such patients should be under the control of a dispensary. Fighting against smoking is of particular importance in the prevention of pulmonary emphysema.

Emphysema is a type of COPD (chronic obstructive pulmonary disease). COPD is a group of lung diseases that make it hard to breathe and get worse over time. The other main type of COPD is chronic bronchitis. Most people with COPD have both emphysema and chronic bronchitis, but how severe each type is can be different from person to person. Emphysema affects the air sacs in your lungs. Normally, these sacs are elastic or stretchy. When you breathe in, each air sac fills up with air, like a small balloon. When you breathe out, the air sacs

deflate, and the air goes out. In emphysema, the walls between many of the air sacs in the lungs are damaged. This causes the air sacs to lose their shape and become floppy. The damage also can destroy the walls of the air sacs, leading to fewer and larger air sacs instead of many tiny ones. This makes it harder for your lungs to move oxygen in and carbon dioxide out of your body. The cause of emphysema is usually long-term exposure to irritants that damage your lungs and the airways. In the United States, cigarette smoke is the main cause. Pipe, cigar, and other types of tobacco smoke can also cause emphysema, especially if you inhale them. Exposure to other inhaled irritants can contribute to emphysema. These include secondhand smoke, air pollution, and chemical fumes or dusts from the environment or workplace.

Emphysema develops over time and involves the gradual damage of lung tissue, specifically the destruction of the alveoli (tiny air sacs). Gradually, this damage causes the air sacs to rupture and create one big air pocket instead of many small ones. This reduction in the lung surface area traps air in the damaged tissue and prevents oxygen from moving through the bloodstream. Additionally, this blockage causes the lungs to slowly overfill and makes breathing increasingly more difficult.

- Over three million people in the United States have been diagnosed with emphysema.
- Emphysema is one of the most preventable respiratory illnesses because it is so strongly linked to smoking. Air pollutants, an alpha-1 antitrypsin deficiency, and respiratory infections can also play a role, but smoking is considered the number one cause.
- Signs and symptoms of emphysema take years to develop, but once they start, they generally include shortness of breath, coughing with mucus, wheezing and chest tightness.

- Several tests are needed to diagnose emphysema including chest X-rays, pulse oximetry, spirometry and other pulmonary function tests, arterial blood gas test and electrocardiogram (ECG).
- Though emphysema cannot be cured, many treatments are available to help manage symptoms. Bronchodilator medications relax the muscles, anti-inflammatory medication can reduce airway inflammation, oxygen therapy can assist patients who need help breathing. Non-surgical endobronchial valves may be placed to allow trapped air to escape. In extreme situations, lung volume reduction surgery can relieve pressure by removing a portion of diseased lung tissue or a lung transplant may be considered.

Overinflation of the air sacs is a result of a breakdown of the alveoli walls. It causes a decrease in respiratory function and breathlessness. Damage to the air sacs can't be fixed. It causes permanent breakdown in the lower lung tissue. Pulmonary emphysema is part of a group of lung diseases called COPD (chronic obstructive pulmonary disease). COPD causes airflow blockage and breathing problems. The 2 most common conditions of COPD are chronic bronchitis and emphysema. Along with a complete health history and physical exam, your healthcare provider may do pulmonary function tests. These tests help measure the lungs' ability to exchange oxygen and carbon dioxide. The tests are often done with special machines into which you breathe. This device measures how fast you can blow air out of your lungs. Cough, inflammation, and mucus buildup can cause the large airways in the lungs to slowly narrow. This slows the speed of air leaving the lungs. This measurement is very important in seeing how well or how poorly the disease is being controlled. Emphysema and chronic bronchitis are airflow-limited states contained within the disease state known as chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). Just as asthma is no longer grouped with COPD, the current definition of COPD put forth by the Global Initiative for

Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease (GOLD) also no longer distinguishes between emphysema and chronic bronchitis. Emphysema is pathologically defined as an abnormal permanent enlargement of air spaces distal to the terminal bronchioles, accompanied by the destruction of alveolar walls and without obvious fibrosis. This process leads to reduced gas exchange, changes in airway dynamics that impair expiratory airflow, and progressive air trapping.

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